

EVALUATING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBER/EPOXY INTERFACES USING THE SLICE COMPRESSION TEST

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SUMMARY: Properties of the fiber/matrix interface in SiO₂/epoxy and SiC/epoxy composites are investigated using the slice compression test (SCT) for the single fiber, where the specimen is loaded and unloaded between two different plates. It is found that the interfacial debonding proceeds from the polished surface at a soft plate side and that the fiber protrusion occurs after unloading. Interfacial shear-sliding stress is obtained based on the constant shear-sliding stress analysis which employing the obtained protrusion length. It is demonstrated that the experimental value is in a good agreement with that from the other technique on the same system. However, it is pointed out analytically that the applied stress to the specimen has a limitation due to Poisson's effect when calculating the interfacial shear-sliding stress.

KEYWORDS: slice compression test, polymer matrix composite, interface, interfacial shear sliding stress, poison's effect, debonding.

INTRODUCTION

Parameters that affect the stress transfer in polymer matrix composites (PMCs) are related to interfacial properties such as the interfacial shear sliding stress and debonding stress. These parameters, which are often incorporated in the analytical interface models, are rarely measured directly. Several techniques have been developed. Micro-indentation¹ and fiber push-out are typical methods to evaluate these properties. However, these tests evaluate interfacial properties of only one fiber at a time, and require a special indenter and complicated testing machines, which can not be applied to the composite subject to the service load. PMC is also used under hostile conditions (eg; cryogenic and radiation environments) for applications such as thermal insulating superconductivity support systems and liquid hydrogen tanks. Under such conditions, it is almost impossible to measure the interfacial properties.

The slice compression test (SCT)²⁻⁶ can be used to extract interfacial properties by loading/unloading a polished slice specimen of the composite which is cut normal to the axial fiber direction between a soft, low modulus plate, and a hard, high modulus plate. As the fiber has usually a higher modulus than matrix in the PMC, fiber protrusion occurs during loading at soft plate sides. During the unloading process, the protruded fiber relaxes back into the matrix, retaining residual protrusion after complete unloading because of interfacial friction. Although the technique is simple, doesn't require special machines, and can be used under cryogenic conditions, it has never been applied to the PMC, since it is initially developed for ceramic systems. Also, the applicability of the existing analysis has only met with limited success.

The objective of this paper is to apply the SCT to the PMC and clarify the fiber-protrusion behavior in the PMC system. Also, Poisson's effect which influences the fiber protrusion length and the interfacial shear-sliding stress is analyzed.

EXPERIMENT

Specimen

Epoxy resin (Epikote828, $E_m=3000\text{MPa}$) containing single glass fiber (SiO_2 , $E_f=78\text{GPa}$), diameter $a=200\mu\text{m}$, and SiC fiber ($E_f=406\text{GPa}$), diameter $a=140\mu\text{m}$, were used. Mechanical properties of constituents are listed in Table 1. The specimens were cut normal to the fiber direction, thickness of $6\pm 0.5\text{ mm}$, and the surfaces of the specimens were polished up to $1\mu\text{m}$ with diamond paste (see Fig.1). However, the interface between fiber and matrix was debonded from the surface for a large number of polished specimens.

Fig. 1: Geometry and dimensions of specimen

Table. 1: Materials properties of constituents

	SiO_2	SiC	Epoxy
E (GPa)	78	406	3.0
ν	0.14	0.15	0.37
$\alpha_z(10^{-6}/\text{K})$	0.5	5	65
$\alpha_r(10^{-6}/\text{K})$	0.5	2.63	65

Fig. 2: Schematic drawing of SCT

Experimental procedure

The slice compression test is carried out using a universal-testing machine as shown in Fig. 2. The specimen was located parallel to the loading direction and sandwiched between soft plate, annealed Al1050 (thickness: 3mm, $E=60\text{MPa}$, proportional limit: $\approx 10\text{MPa}$), and hard plate, SUS 303. A various compressive stress was applied to the specimen through the soft plate at a loading rate of 0.05 mm/min. When the load reached a certain point, the load was kept for 30 seconds, then unloaded at the same rate. It is noted that the applied stress was below the compressive yielding stress of the epoxy matrix ($\approx 60\text{MPa}$). The data obtained from the SCT consists of the peak load and the residual fiber protrusion after complete unloading. The residual fiber protrusion length was measured by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Boundary condition at surface

The idealized model used in the present study is shown Fig. 3. Two kinds of boundary conditions of the stresses at the soft plate side have been proposed to analyze the interfacial shear-sliding stress. One assumes that the stress is uniformly distributed³⁻⁵, the other assumes that the fiber stress is always larger than the applied stress while the matrix stress is smaller⁶. However, it is not obvious which boundary condition is appropriate for this model. In the present study, parameter m is defined as follows;

$$\sigma_{zf}^u = m\sigma_0, \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{zm}^u = \frac{b^2 - ma^2}{b^2 - a^2} \sigma_0. \quad (2)$$

Radial stress at the surface due to Poisson's effect, σ_r^p , can be derived from the above equations and the present model, such that⁵

$$\sigma_r^p = \frac{\sigma_0}{D} \left\{ m \frac{E_m}{E_f} \nu_f - \frac{b^2 - ma^2}{b^2 - a^2} \nu_f \right\} \quad (3)$$

where D is a constant.

The result, which is computed using $\text{SiO}_2/\text{epoxy}$ system in Table 1, shows that the radial stress at the soft plate side is almost independent of m in this study (Fig. 4). Therefore, uniform stress distribution can be adopted in this study.

Fig. 3: Composite cylinder model for SCT analysis

Fig. 4: Interfacial radial stress at surface due to Poisson's effect

Fiber protrusion behavior

Typical examples of SiO₂ and SiC fiber protrusion at each applied stress level are shown in Fig. 5. Displacement of fiber protrusion, Δu_0 , can be measured after unloading, and the protruded length increases with increasing the applied compressive stress σ^* . From the *in-situ* observation, the interfacial debonding propagation takes place from the soft plate side when the applied stress reached the critical value. On the other hand, the interfacial debonding is not observed at the opposite side (the hard plate side).

Fig. 5: Typical SEM photographs showing the fiber protrusion with increasing applied stress: above SiO₂, below SiC

The measured fiber protruded lengths of SiO₂ and SiC are plotted in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 as a function of compressive applied stress, respectively. As clearly shown in both figures, the normalized fiber protrusion lengths increase with increasing the applied stress. However, the linear relationship between the applied stress and the normalized fiber protrusion is vanished at $\sigma^* \approx 50$ MPa in the SiO₂/epoxy system and at $\sigma^* \approx 40$ MPa in the SiC/epoxy system.

Fig. 6: Dependence of fiber protrusion on applied stress: SiO₂/epoxy

Fig. 7: Dependence of fiber protrusion on applied stress: SiC/epoxy

Upper limit of applied stress

The parameters which affect the fiber protrusion behavior and interfacial sliding are (i) residual radial stress and (ii) radial stress due to Poisson's effect. In the PMC system, residual radial stress prior to loading is usually compressive because α_f is less than α_m . In case of $\nu_f < \nu_m$, this compressive stress decreases due to Poisson's effect with an increase of applied stress. The residual radial σ_r^r stress after fabrication is given by⁷,

$$\sigma_r^r = A \left[\frac{1 + \nu_f}{E_f} + \frac{f}{1-f} \frac{1 + \nu_m}{E_m} \right] (\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where A is a constant which is determined by material properties, f is a fiber volume fraction, and ΔT is temperature change.

The obtained value is $\sigma_r^r = -11.5$ MPa in SiO₂/epoxy system which is in good agreement with the numerical analysis. The interfacial shear sliding is only generated by the premise that the resultant interfacial radial stress is compressive, such that

$$\sigma_r^p + \sigma_r^r < 0 \quad (5)$$

The contact condition can be derived from eqs. (3), (4) and (5) with $m=1$. And, the upper limit of applied stress is expected at $\sigma_r^p + \sigma_r^r = 0$. The obtained value in this study is $\sigma_0 = -44.3$ MPa with SiO₂/epoxy system. It might be said that the proportional limits of the normalized protruded lengths in Fig.6 and 7 are related to Poisson's effect.

The interface debonding and sliding process of PMC interface using SCT is schematically shown in Fig.8. After initiation, a crack goes down from soft plate side with interfacial sliding. Fiber protrusion length increases with an increase of applied stress. However, the sliding between fiber and matrix vanishes at the debonded region when the applied stress reaches the critical value. Finally, the interfacial debonding propagates without contact. This phenomenon indicates that a maximum applied stress exists when calculating the interfacial shear-sliding stress.

Fig. 8: Debonding process of PMC with SCT

Interfacial shear sliding stress

An approximate solution for relationship between the fiber protruded length Δu_0 and a constant interfacial frictional stress τ_s is given by²⁻⁴

$$\tau_s = \frac{a(1-f)(E_f - E_m)^2(\sigma^*)^2}{8E_f E_m E_c \Delta u_0} \quad (6)$$

where $E_c = fE_f + (1-f)E_m$.

The calculated interfacial shear-sliding stresses are plotted in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 as a function of the compressive applied stress. It is noted that the SCT is performed under the upper limit to avoid Poisson's effect. The obtained interfacial shear-sliding stress is independent of the applied stress. And, the average value is $\tau_s = 11.9$ MPa and $\tau_s = 29.9$ MPa for SiO₂/epoxy and SiC/epoxy, respectively; the former is in good agreement with that from the other technique, the push-out test, on the same system⁸. This concurrency is encouraging as it implies that the test is applicable to PMC systems.

Fig. 9: Dependence of shear sliding stress on applied stress: SiO₂

Fig. 10: Dependence of shear sliding stress on applied stress: SiC

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The following conclusions can be drawn from this work.

- (1) The slice compression test is used to evaluate the interfacial properties of SiO₂/epoxy and SiC/epoxy composite. The obtained interfacial shear-sliding stress is compared with the other technique, the push-out test, on the same system.
- (2) From the *in-situ* observation, interface debonding starts at the soft plate side with the increase of applied stress. Otherwise, debonding propagation is not observed at the hard plate side.
- (3) Fiber protruded length after unloading increases with the increase of applied stress. However, this increasing rate alternates when the compressive stress overcomes a particular value because of Poisson's effect, i.e., the upper limit of the applied stress for interfacial contact exists.
- (4) The interfacial shear-sliding stress is obtained based on the constant shear-sliding stress analysis employing the obtained protrusion length. The calculated value below the upper limit of the applied stress is $\tau_s = 11.9$ MPa and $\tau_s = 29.9$ MPa for SiO₂/epoxy system and SiC/epoxy system, respectively. And, these experimental values are in good agreement with those from the other technique, the push-out test, on the same system.

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